

A Study on Awareness of GST among Commerce Students in Theni District

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Abstract

Implementation of GST would be a very important in the field of indirect tax reforms in India. Some of respondents gave a positive feedback about Implementation of GST. "A study on awareness of GST among commerce students in Theni District." This study based on personal interviews with commerce students. This study based on primary data which are collected by distribution of questionnaire.

Keywords: GST, Rate structure.

Introduction

"Goods and Services Tax" is a comprehensive indirect tax on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services which was implemented throughout India from 1st July, 2017. It replaced almost all indirect taxes levied by Central and State Governments (e.g. VAT, Service Tax, Exercise Duty, Octroi, etc. Goods and Service Tax is levied and collected at each stage of sale or purchase of goods or services based on the input tax credit method. This method allows GST-registered business to claim to the value of GST they paid on purchase of goods or services as part of their normal commercial activity. Administrative responsibility would generally rest GST Council to levy tax on goods and services.

History

Goods and Services Tax ("GST") is a norm in more than 150 countries of the world and India is soon to join the guild. The start towards a true Value added regime was made with the introduction of MODVAT by the Central government and in the state level taxation with the replacement of sales tax by state Value Added Tax ("VAT") laws. India gets its first discussion paper on GST released by the ECSFM on November 10, 2009.

GST Tax Rate

- GST rates are divided into five categories which are 0%, 5%, 12%, 18%, 28%.

- All the basic need requirement goods are placed in 0% category like food grains, bread, salt, books, etc...
- Goods like paneer, packed food, tea, coffee, etc... are placed under 5% category.
- Mobiles, sweets, medicine are under 18%category.
- All other remaining luxury items are placed under the last head of 28%.
- Petrol, gas, crude oil, diesel, etc,... are still out from the criteria of GST

Review of Literature

Ethical Ahmed and satie plodder (2009) studied Goods and Services Tax (GST) reforms “Intergovernmental Consideration in India”. They found that introduction of GST will sustain smooth and transparent tax system in India. But the success of GST is dependent on its rational implementation.

Objectives of the Study

- To know about the GST.
- To find out the profile of the sample respondents.
- To analysis the awareness of GST.

Scope of Study

This paper covers “A study on Awareness of GST among commerce students” in Theni district.

Data Collection

Both Primary and secondary data used in the present study.

Primary data: The data was collected through personal research in the form of questionnaire from 65 respondents.

Secondary data: Data was collected from various journals, books and magazines.

Tools For Analysis

Percentage

Analysis and Interpretation

Table Socio economic status of the respondents

variables	Categories	No of respondents	percentage
Gender	Male	30	46
	Female	35	54
Age of respondents			
Age	17-20 years	43	66
	21-23 years	10	15
	Above 23 years	12	19
Education qualification of the respondents			
Education qualification	B. Com	43	66
	M. Com	10	15
	M. Phil	7	11
	Ph.D	5	8

Marital status of the respondents			
Marital status	Married	35	54
	Un married	30	46
Total		65	100

From the above table interpret that majority of the respondents 35 (54%) is under female category, 43 (66%) respondents are under age group of between 17-20years; under Educational qualification of the respondents, most of the respondents are 43 (66%) studying B.com,and(54%) of the respondents are married

Category of College

There are 3 categories of college where respondents were working. The following tables explain the category of college of the respondents

Table

S.no	Types	No of the respondents	Percentage
1	Private	20	31
2	Aided	33	51
3	Government	12	18
Total		65	100

From above Table No 1.2 show that, 33 (51%) of the respondents are studying Aided college, 20 (31%) of the respondents are studying private college, 12 (18%) of the respondents are studying government colleges.

Analysis of Students Awareness on the Implementation of GST

Table

S.No	Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage	
1	GST Implementation in India	Yes	35	54
		No	30	46
	Total	65	100	
2	Nature of GST	Yes	20	31
		No	45	69
	Total	65	100	
3	Mechanism and applicability of GST	Yes	62	95
		No	3	5
	Total	65	100	
4	GST council	Yes	58	89
		No	7	11
	Total	65	100	
5	Slab rates	Yes	57	88
		No	8	12
	Total	65	100	

From above table No. 1.3 show that, 54% of the respondents are aware of GST being implemented in India, 69% of them are not aware that it is an Indirect tax, 95% of them know that Mechanism and applicability of GST, 89% of the respondents know that the regulatory body for GST is GST & 88% are aware about the existing slab rates.

Findings

From the survey concluded in Theni district the following finds were divided from total of 65 respondents.

- 35 respondents were Female
- From these study 43 respondents belongs to the age group 17-20 years of category.
- 43 respondents were studying the educational qualification of B.Com.
- Of the 65 respondents 35 respondents were married.

Sugession

- It is an idea that GST should be incorporated in the Commerce Educational subjects.
- Awareness and knowledge about GST should be conducted through regular seminars and workshops.
- Practical knowledge about GST should be spread widely by professionals like C.A's, LAW-YER, etc.

Conclusion

Students and young generation infact are elements or impact asset in the country and will be leader in the future. There will continue to implement the national development program to achive vision 2020. No doubt that GST will give India a world class tax system by grabbing different treatment to manufacturing and service sectors. If is the needs of every student to have awareness above the new GST Regime. The overall finding show that even though the student were awareness of the governments initiative to implement of Goods and Service Tax (GST) but they still have medium level in knowledge relation to this matter.

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